

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Development Toward Self-Sufficiency: The Marketing Blend in the Tourism Community of Hutatinggi, Samosir.

Elfitra Desy Surya

Universitas Pembangunan Pancabudi Medan, North Sumatera, Indonesia

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Abstract**Objective**

This study aims to assess the extent to which the influence of the marketing mix on tourists' sustained excursions to Hutatinggi tourist hamlet, Samosir Regency, is influenced by satisfaction.

Methods

The questionnaire was utilized as a tool for collecting data and distributed to a total of 265 participants. The data analysis technique used is structural equation modeling (SEM) with the SMART PLS program.

Results

The results suggest that elements such as the product, price, location, procedures, and physical evidence have a favorable effect on visitors' satisfaction, however this effect is not statistically significant. Similarly, the factors of promotion, people, packaging, and positioning also contribute to visitors' satisfaction, albeit their impact is not statistically significant. In addition, the study demonstrates that promotion, individuals, packaging, positioning, satisfaction, sustainability, sustainable packaging influenced by satisfaction, and sustainable positioning influenced by satisfaction all exert a positive and statistically significant impact on the number of visits made by visitors to the Hutatinggi tourist village in Samosir Regency.

Keywords

Marketing Mix, Satisfaction, Sustainable, Samosir, Indonesia

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Corresponding author: Elfitra Desy Surya (suryaelfitra7@gmail.com)

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Introduction

Resort villages in Indonesia are experiencing a growing trend in popularity. This notion is an extracurricular initiative that aims to develop students in alignment with the goals of the university. This tendency is associated with an increase in the number of tourists visiting resorts. Tourist villages in Indonesia possess immense potential within the tourism industry and have emerged as a prominent entity in the market. Various aspects of village life, such as the local culture, natural surroundings, handicrafts, and customs, have the potential to attract tourists (Buhalis, 2015). This park provides genuine encounters and enables long-range interaction with the local population. Developing tourist towns to enhance the local community's income, preserve cultural heritage, and promote sustainable tourism is an unconventional approach. In Indonesia, numerous localities, like Kabupaten Toba Samosir, have embraced the notion of "tourism" as a means to enhance the tourism industry. This indicates that "tourism" has emerged as a prevailing phenomenon, as it enables the local community to generate additional revenue and offers visitors a distinctive encounter. Furthermore A tourism environment refers to a conceptual framework developed by the tourism industry to illustrate the factors influencing tourists' destination choices. These factors include image, perception, available information, transportation and communication options, financial resources, and tourists' perspectives (Farber & Hall, 2007).

Three verifiable facts have been established regarding tourism: 1) attracting a greater number of tourists, 2) prolonging the duration of tourists' visits, and 3) increasing the amount of money spent by tourists during their stay. This is the. The company must comprehend four components of the system to achieve this objective: the market, the travel, the destination, and the payment (Gómez-Rico et al., 2023). Implementing a well-designed marketing mix is the most effective strategy to ensure repeated visits from tourists. This refers to a set of tactics employed by a business to elicit the desired reaction from their intended audience. Marketing builders encompass the various assets and strategies that a firm can utilize to acquire new customers and provide existing ones with valuable offerings. The components of the marketing mix demonstrate an effective marketing strategy that will enable the organization to achieve its marketing objectives by engaging customers and providing them with something valuable (Amstrong & Kotler, 2017). Table 1 provides detailed information on each category of tourist town.

Table 1. Classification of Tourist Village Development in Indonesia

No	Status	Description	Number of Villages (until 2022)
1.	Star Up	a. The village has the potential that develop as a tourist destination b. The development of tourism infrastructure is still limited c. Few or very few tourists from the surrounding community have visited the village d. The community's awareness has not yet grown to its potential e. Assistance from other stakeholders (e.g., government, private, university) in developing a village as a tourist destination is highly needed f. The development of the village as a tourist destination still utilizes the village funds g. The management of the tourist village is still fully under the locals	2.318
2.	Developing	a. The village is known as an emerging tourist destination b. Some visitors visit the village not only from the surrounding community but also from outside the area	941

No	Status	Description	Number of Villages (until 2022)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> c. There are promising opportunities for the development of infrastructure and tourism facilities d. Employment opportunities and economic activity for the community from tourism have been created, although still in the early stages e. The community's awareness of their tourism potential has grown, which can be seen from the f. Utilizing village funds in the development of tourist villages. g. The management of the tourist village is still fully under the locals 	
3.	Developed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. The community is fully aware of the tourism potential, including its development b. The village has become a well-known tourist destination, and there are many visitors for tourists, including foreign tourists c. Tourism facilities and infrastructure are adequate d. The community can manage tourism activities through Pokdarwis or local working groups e. The community has been able to take advantage of village funds in the development of a tourist village f. The tourism village management system has an impact on improving the economy of the community in the village 	281
4.	Self-sufficient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. The local community has provided innovation in developing tourism potential in their village b. The village has become a tourist destination known by foreign countries and has implemented a sustainable concept recognized by the world c. The village's infrastructure is not only adequate but also follows international standards d. The management of the tourist village is carried out collaboratively between sectors and has been going well e. The village can take advantage of digitalization as a form of independent promotion (i.e., able to make promotional materials and sell f. independently through digitalization and technology). 	11

Source: Adapted from Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, 2022

According to Table 1, the majority of tourist villages in Indonesia are currently classified as star-up tourist communities. The research focuses on the tourist village of Hutatinggi, located in Samosir Regency, which is now undergoing development. Out of the overall count of tourist villages in Samosir, there are 50 tourist villages categorized as follows: 35 are classified as start-up, 11 as developing, and 4 as developed. None of the tourist villages have achieved self-sufficiency status. Nevertheless, it appears that Toba Samosir Regency currently lacks a village green space that meets the criteria outlined in Table 2. According to the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, there will be 244 tourist towns that will be officially recognized as separate tourist villages by 2024 (Kemenparekraf, 2022). This study utilized multiple national parks in Samosir Regency as case studies. Hutatinggi National Park, located in Pangururan, is the primary national park in the area (Dwi Aditya Putra, 2022). This village serves as a domicile for the Toba Batak people. According to the 2021 Indonesian Tourism Village Award Event (ADWI), the Huta Tinggi National Park is ranked among the top 50 national parks in Indonesia.

Hutatinggi, a booming tourist village, offers a plethora of activities for travelers. One notable attraction is educational tourism, which allows visitors to gain hands-on experience in milking buffalo and processing the milk. There is a certain gesture that individuals typically do in the vicinity of the tree's main stem, known as dali ni horbo. Additionally, the UNESCO Geosite area encompasses both natural and cultural resources. The processed buffalo milk is commonly referred to as the characteristic Toba Batak cheese. Hutatinggi possesses significant potential, capable of elevating the status of the tourist hamlet from a developing state to an autonomous one. (Kristin Septiyani, 2021) In order to accomplish this, it is imperative that all individuals collaborate in a manner that deviates significantly from their usual practices. This entails active involvement from individuals within the tourist sector, the local government, and a well-integrated infrastructure that is closely aligned with the state's tourism promotion board.

In a study conducted by Katniaty et al. (2023), it was discovered that certain factors such as price, promotion, and physical setting had a notable impact on sales volume. However, variables such as product, location, personnel, and process did not appear to have any apparent influence on sales volumes. According to recent research conducted by Yona Floranika (2022), the marketing mix of the tourist business, which includes product, price, venue, promotion, people, and packaging, now includes partnership as an additional essential aspect. In this study, the author used a novel and inventive approach by incorporating an additional variable, namely the positioning variable, into the marketing mix. This was conducted based on prior research findings.

Figure 1. Number Of Tourist Village Indonesia
Source: Adapted from Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy, 2021(ADWI 2021)

Figure 1 displays the distribution of tourist settlements across Indonesia, with 573 of them concentrated on the island of Sumatra. However, the vast majority of Sumatra Island's inhabitants are still in the first stage of tourism village development. Increasing tourist satisfaction and returning visits is one way that a developing tourist village might work toward becoming an autonomous tourist village.

Literature Review

1. Travel Destination

A vacation site is a location where individuals on vacation go to unwind and indulge in leisure activities (Maitland, 2002). According to Tuohino and Konu (2014), tourist destinations are specific geographical locations that have the ability to attract tourists for a long duration. These destinations consist of different tourist offerings and require certain conditions to be met in order to be successful. As per the research conducted by Brent Ritchie and Crouch in 2010, a tourist destination refers to a combination of various services and facilities that can be obtained as a single package. These services and amenities might vary from particular offerings to more broad ones.

Travel destinations are today recognized as a combination of goods, services, and experiences given by local businesses, as well as a collaborative effort by private and public sectors to cater to the demands of different stakeholders. According to Kottler et al. (2022), tourism destinations are viewed as a commodity product by marketing managers. This means that there is a need to bring together different facilities and services that are specifically intended to meet the needs of tourists (Liao & Chuang, 2020). In order to be considered a tourist attraction, a place must fulfill several requirements, which include having a sufficient amount of land, or "Kawasan," being appealing to tourists, offering satisfactory accommodations and dining options, being easily accessible to tourists, and being effectively administered.

2. Marketing Mix

The tourism marketing mix refers to the set of marketing tools and strategies employed to promote and execute the consumer value proposition. Its purpose is to optimize effectiveness and efficiency, hence resulting in a competitive advantage for the tourism marketing strategy. From the standpoint of the tourism destination market, it is essential to incorporate the customer's value into every aspect of the offering. This collection of elements is referred to as the tourism marketing mix, or simply put, a set of tools used to generate customer value (Hidayah, 2022).

In the tourism services business, the marketing mix is employed to meet the needs of consumers by placing greater emphasis on the quality of tourism attractions, which can be assessed using seven factors (7P): product, price, promotion, location, people, physical evidence, and process (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018). A tourism destination marketing mix is the instrument used to create customer value for tourism locations. Thus, in order to ensure that tourism destinations offer exceptional customer value, it is imperative for tourism destination marketers to develop an outstanding marketing mix. A superior tourist marketing mix is a combination of marketing strategies that offers distinct advantages and is perceived as cost-effective by the intended audience. Unique benefits in the context of tourism destinations refer to advantages that are distinct and not offered by competitors. Indeed, a successful tourism destination must not only be distinct, but it must also offer practical and emotional solutions that surpass those of its competitors. Additionally, it should be enduring or sustainable, meaning that it should not be a temporary attraction that quickly fades away, but rather a destination that can withstand the test of time without relying on trial and error methods. Merely generates a transient fad. Using tourism marketing techniques is essential for growing the value of your clientele in the travel industry. Meanwhile, the most well-known components of a marketing mix are the 4Ps, which were popularized by (Karsono & Salma, 2023) : product, price, placement, and promotion. By expanding the traditional marketing mix of product, price, place, and promotion to include packaging, programming, partnership, and people,

Morrison (2013) has developed a specialized model designed exclusively for the promotion of tourism locations. Currently, the 4Ps framework in marketing is considered to be too focused on the producer's perspective, using language that prioritizes the producer. To address this, it is necessary to update the framework to be more customer-oriented, using language that prioritizes the consumer. Additionally, the framework should be aligned with the principle of customer value, which serves as a guiding philosophy. The 7Ps model of service marketing, developed by (Rainanto et al., 2023), and the 8Ps model, developed by (Saputra et al., 2018), share similar principles. However, Morrison's model expands on Booms and Bitner's model by incorporating packaging, programming, and partnerships, while the latter model solely emphasizes the product itself. Product components in the marketing mix of the tourism industry encompass the 4P, 7P, and 8P frameworks.

3. Product

The term "product" in the context of travel sales strategy pertains to the emphasis placed on the quality and quantity of travel-related goods and services offered to visitors. The marketing principles that focus on products are the most essential and widely implemented by almost every business in the tourism industry. According to Kotler (2016), a product refers to any item or service that is made available in the market with the intention of capturing attention, being purchased, used, and fulfilling wants. A product is defined as something that can fulfill the essential requirements of consumers and their wishes for contentment, regardless of whether the product has a tangible form or not (Gunawan, 2022). Emphasizing the quality of items is crucial for boosting tourist traffic and should not be disregarded. Tourism products encompass the offerings that tourists can acquire knowledge about, engage with, and buy while on their journey. When a tourist site provides superior services and products, visitors are more inclined to spend their money at that location. Product or tourism goods can be categorized into two fundamental groups: tangible items that are seen and can be physically interacted with (goods), and intangible items that are not visible or touchable (services). All intangible services that tourists can enjoy are classified as jasa. (Fatihudin & Firmansyah, 2019) contend that all types of products, regardless of their physicality, can be presented to prospective clients with the aim of fulfilling their desires and requirements.

4. Price

The word "travel price" denotes the pre-established expense associated with utilizing a service or acquiring a product related to travel. Within the realm of acquiring products and services, the term "price" denotes the amount of money that must be spent in order to receive the desired item or service. As per the findings of (Anjani et al., 2019), the worth of something refers to the total amount of money or other forms of compensation (such as products or services) that are given in exchange for the privilege of owning or utilizing that particular thing. Establishing prices is of utmost importance for participants in the tourism sector as they have the potential to impact several aspects such as revenue generation and the availability of specific products. Therefore, it is advantageous for all parties involved to provide affordable products and services in the tourism sector. According to Tariq Khan's research in 2014, the price of a product or service plays a significant role in consumers' decision-making process on whether or not to make a purchase.

5. Promotion

Marketing principles, such as promotion, play a vital role in influencing the number of tourists. Advertising is the act of disseminating information about a product or service. Tourism marketing refers to the deliberate actions used by the travel sector to inform, captivate, and eventually convince prospective visitors to reserve a journey and avail themselves of the available services (Bunda Mulia, 2021). Effective marketing techniques will attract tourists to visit and motivate communities to embrace their presence. Therefore, traditional manual methods of promoting tourism are no longer required. Instead, the utilization of advanced information technology, such as travel apps like tourism, can effectively reach every individual and tourist worldwide. Traveler-friendly apps, such as e-tourism and others, that are available to everyone, will attract a larger number of people to travel. Implementing this method to promote tourism will significantly influence the number of tourists visiting.

6. Place

The place is a tourist destination that tourists will visit. (Ahmad Afan Zain, 2022) states that place (related to the delivery system) is a combination of location and decisions about distribution channels. This relates to how services are delivered to consumers and where the strategic location is. Location also relates to where the company should be headquartered and carry out its operations or business activities. Determining a tourist destination must take into account the transportation that will be used. Ease of access to tourist destinations at appropriate costs must be taken into account in this tourism marketing principle (Nosalska & Mazurek, 2019). Apart from that, the accuracy of the location of branch offices, head offices of tourism marketers, or other tangible facilities will determine the demand for tourists to make tourist visits. Therefore, the existing facilities and infrastructure in tourist destinations need to be improved, the quality is easy and affordable, and transportation facilities are available to tourist destinations.

7. People

The main target of tourism marketing is the human population, often known as rakyat. The existence of human beings is essential for the implementation of marketing strategies in the tourism industry. Hence, the influx of tourists to a destination is significantly influenced by the capacity, competence, and expertise of the human resources within the tourism business, specifically in terms of marketing tourism and enticing tourists (Jain, 2013). It is essential for all stakeholders involved in the organization and implementation of tourist activities to have access to proficient tourism marketing experts. This includes the government, the local community, and the business sector. The human resources in the tourist business should obtain certification in order to promote products and destinations in a professional manner. This is due to the fact that individuals stationed in the outermost regions of the security forces have the most immediate and direct engagement with tourists. Opting for an inappropriate tourist SDM can lead to a decrease in visitor numbers, and conversely, selecting the right one can result in an increase. According to Veronica (2017), service providers play a crucial role in determining the quality of service in service marketing.

8. Process

Process or transformation strategy is a business approach to turning resources into goods and services. The goal of process strategy is to find a way to produce goods and services that meets customer requirements and product specifications within cost and other managerial constraints. The process is a combination of all activities consisting of several stages, namely procedures, work schedules, mechanisms, activities, and routine matters where services are produced and delivered to consumers (Siripipatthanakul, 2021).

9. Physical of Evidence

Physical evidence refers to tangible objects or substances that can be observed or measured, including the surrounding environment. The environmental elements are the most prominent aspect while considering the circumstance. Physical evidence plays a direct role in influencing consumers' purchasing and utilization decisions regarding the products and services being given. According to Tiana and Setyawati (2012), the intangible nature of services makes it difficult for potential clients to evaluate a service before using it.

10. Packaging

Packing, commonly referred to as packaging, is an activity that encompasses the design and production of a product's packaging material to ensure it fulfills its intended function of safeguarding the contents of the product, as stated by Kumar Agariya et al. in 2012. (Anjani et al., 2019) further elucidates that the term "packaging" encompasses the strategic and creative process involved in designing and producing a product's container or wrapping material. Packaging is an essential asset for the tourism sector. The primary motivator of tourist numbers is the interest in the packaging of both items and tourist locations. Although color and shape are significant factors in the packing process, it is equally crucial to focus on the design and other pertinent information to attract travelers to your site.

Destination marketing is the act of combining several tourism-related products and services into one attractive package for marketing purposes. Branding in the marketing sector of the travel industry can assist in distinguishing items from competitors, creating unique identities, and communicating the value of the product to potential purchasers. Strategic planning is essential for tourism development to effectively cater to the requirements of tourists while simultaneously safeguarding the integrity of the local culture. Active involvement of the community in the creation of novel tourism packages is crucial for the long-term viability and satisfaction of both residents and tourists (Kumar Agariya et al., 2012).

Community participation can help generate interest in and enthusiasm for new tourism offerings, boosting the hospitality industry as a whole. This includes the development of novel tourism products such as traditional cuisine packaging designs, which can be used to attract a wider audience and spur more investment in the tourism sector. This program's careful planning and implementation is a crucial component of increasing the competitiveness of tourist products. An assortment of carefully crafted and attractively priced tourist goods is sure to contribute to a memorable vacation. Packaging is the bundling of several services and tourist activities into one price offer. However, programming is a branch of technology that deals with automation, which is the systematic execution of a series of steps in order to achieve a predetermined goal.

11. Positioning

According to (Kertajaya, 2004) positioning is the process of developing a company's offerings and image in order to create a distinctive niche in the marketplace. The goal of positioning is to establish a company's brand across a wide audience of consumers in order to maximize the company's profit potential. A positioning strategy is a type of business strategy with the goal of making a company's products and services more valuable than those of competitors in order to attract and retain loyal customers, counteract the pressure of rival firms in the same market, and boost overall performance. Market standing, often known as a company's standing in the minds of consumers relative to competing brands and products, is an important indicator of success in any industry. For consumers to perceive a product or company in a particular light, its identity must be developed through market positioning, also known as market position (Borah et al., 2023). Products are "positioned" when their relative market and consumer value is determined in relation to similar offerings from competing businesses (Greenstone et al., 2020). Product or brand positioning is the strategic process of marketing a product in a certain way to establish distinct image in the minds of target consumers and encourage repeat purchases (Sharp, B; Sharp, 1997)

12. Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction can be defined as "the emotion of joy or dismay that results from comparing the actual performance of a product with its expected performance"(Anand et al., 2023). Indicators include product quality, price, service quality, emotional appeal, cost, and convenience. For a customer to be satisfied, the chosen alternative must produce the same or better outcome than was expected, while dissatisfaction arises when the actual outcome falls short of expectations (Lee et al., 2011). Tourist satisfaction is seen as an integral part of travelers' overall satisfaction with their trip experience (Kastenholz et al., 2018) Satisfaction among tourists can be measured by their emotional reactions to the services they receive (for instance, the quality of the food, lodging, and transportation they received), and this satisfaction has a positive effect on the tourists' desire to return (Ince & Bowen, 2011). Several studies have linked happiness with long-term goals for action.

13. Sustainable

Sustainable commonly used in the context of tourism, refers to the practice of passing on a region's natural resources to future generations without harming them, by ensuring that protection and use are balanced, and by managing tourist hotspots within their ecological means. support and guarantee long-term development in tourist hotspots (Hariss et al., 2022) Long-term tourism is defined by (Hardy et al., 2002) as the type of tourism that ensures future generations can benefit from today's energy sources while preventing environmental degradation, in societies where people continue to live in the same place indefinitely. While there is a wide range of opinions on the topic of all-inclusive resorts, the United Nations World Tourism Organization states that this is based on striking a balance between economic, social, and environmental concept (Josep A. Ivars-Baida, 2016) According to the UNWTO once

again, improving social, cultural, and economic standards while also protecting the environment is essential for ensuring the continued growth of regional tourism as a whole (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2023). In this context, it is important to encourage local food consumption, which is seen as an essential part of the long-term success of the tourism industry (Zolotovskiy, 2023) and contributes to the happiness of visitors.

METHODOLOGY

This study will be conducted from April 2023 to July 2023 and will involve conducting in-depth interviews and observing tourists who visit the Hutatinggi tourist village in the Samosir regency. The selection of respondents will be based on predetermined characteristics. This is important for determining whether they have visited Hutatinggi's tourist village more than once and their overall experience, with the aim of encouraging repeat visits from vacationers. The data collected from interviews will be discussed on a daily basis during office hours. Microsoft Word will be used to store information related to fields and meetings. Previous researchers have examined various factors in this study, but they have only utilized the 7P and 8P frameworks. Therefore, this study will adopt and adapt relevant literature to develop a measurement for the construct variable, expanding the marketing mix to include an additional variable, the positioning variable, as presented in Table 1.

The questionnaire was created with the constructs enumerated in Table 1. The importance of each of the nine components of the marketing mix - product, price, promotion, location, staff, process, physical proof, packaging, and positioning - is evaluated by comparing them to a set of standards. As an illustration, product quality is assessed based on five indications, price is evaluated using five indicators, promotion is measured against five indicators, location is compared using five indicators, staff performance is judged using five indicators, and so forth. The physical evidence was assessed based on four factors, the packing was assessed based on four indicators, and the positioning was assessed based on four indicators. Two survey questions assess metrics of passenger happiness, specifically gauging respondents' agreement with the statement "I was satisfied with the experience." Long-term interest in a place can be measured using three markers, such as the inclination to revisit the specific attraction. The evaluation of all construct variables was conducted using a 5-point Likert scale, with a rating of 1 indicating "complete disagreement" and a rating of 5 indicating "complete agreement." The questionnaire is provided in Indonesian to guarantee a comprehensive understanding of the terminology and instructions prior to commencing the data collection procedure. We utilize a statistical method called Partial Least Squares (PLS) for variational structural equation modeling, from an analytical standpoint. Utilized for assessing estimate models, structural models, and doing hypothesis testing. Since the data in this study does not adhere to a normal distribution, Partial Least Squares (PLS) is the suitable method of analysis.

The data analysis in this study utilized the Path Analysis method and the Smart PLS (Partial Least Square) software. PLS is a technique that effectively handles large amounts of response and explanatory variation simultaneously. It is capable of managing multiple independent variables even in the presence of multicollinearity. After conducting a convergence validity test, a structural model test, and a t-test of hypothesis validity, the significance values in the coefficient tables were examined at a confidence level of 95% or a significance level of 0.05. This information is based on the findings of Sarstedt (2019).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 265 participants completed all the questions on the questionnaire, which was directly handed to tourists in the Hutatinggi tourist village. Visitors who have been Hutatinggi's tourist village on at least two occasions are qualified to complete a questionnaire regarding the area. The survey's demographic information was completed by a higher percentage of women (58.5%) compared to males (41.5%). The age distribution of the respondents was as follows: 20-29 percent, 30-39 percent, and 40-plus percent. The respondents represent a diverse array of professional backgrounds, including a small percentage from the public sector (6.5%), state-owned enterprises (9%), private sector (29.5%), academia (22%), and domestic vocations (6.0%). The majority of respondents who completed the questionnaire were S1 graduates, accounting for 79.5% of the total. This was followed by SMA graduates at 14.5%, and S2 graduates at 6%. The median monthly salary, based on the respondents' various jobs, falls between Rp 2,000,000,000 and Rp 5,000,000,000 for 50% of the respondents. 25% of the respondents earn Rp 2,000,000,000, while 15% earn between Rp 5,000,000,000 and Rp 10,000,000,000. Only 9.5% of the respondents earn more than Rp 10,000,000,000.

Once the data is gathered from the interviewee, it is subjected to analysis using a Partial Least Squares (PLS) test in order to examine presuppositions and hypotheses. Partial Least Squares (PLS) is a statistical technique that is employed to effectively handle and analyze substantial amounts of response and explanatory variation simultaneously. Although the variables in issue exhibit multicollinearity, PLS is still able to effectively handle a substantial number of independent variables. The method of PLS analysis can be divided into two main components: outside model analysis and inner model analysis. The validity and reliability of research instruments can be evaluated by an outer-model analysis. The external model can be evaluated using the metrics of convergence, construction, discrimination, and composite validity. The internal model is expected to be utilized for the assessment of metrics such as R square and goodness of fit. Once valid and reliable data have been established, it is possible to test hypotheses.

1. Outer Model

An outer-model analysis is conducted to assess the validity and reliability of a research instrument. Assessing the accuracy and consistency of a measurement tool enables one to evaluate its effectiveness in measuring certain variables, as well as the consistency of measurements obtained from different tools at various times and places. Values for convergence, construction, and composite dependability can be utilized to assess the resilience of an external model.

- a. In the context of convergent validity, the outer loading parameter is utilized to compute the reliability value of convergence. Items are deemed statistically valid when their loading factors exceed 0.7 for all routes connecting constituent elements and individual preferences. All the things in the previous table have values as the ultimate outcome.
- b. The loading factor is more than 0.7, indicating that all items in this study are statistically valid and can be utilized in future studies. Construct validity, also known as *validitas konstruk*, refers to the extent to which a measurement tool accurately measures the theoretical construct it is intended to measure. The construct validity of a test can provide insight into the extent to

which it can accurately assess the soundness of a theory's design. A structure is considered effective when its AVE value exceeds 0.5.

Table 2. Construct Validity

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Product (X1)	0,680
Price (X2)	0,765
Promotion (X3)	0,785
Place (X4)	0,682
Process (X5)	0,805
People (X6)	0,776
Physical of Eviden (X7)	0,748
Packaging (X8)	0,725
Positioning (X9)	0,789
Satisfaction (Y1)	0,779
Sustainable (Y2)	0,733

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Table 2 data unequivocally demonstrates that all AVE values for the various factors in this investigation surpass 0.5. The research variables in question can be confidently deemed to possess strong construct validity. Component Reliability (also known as Reliability Komposit) is a measure of the likelihood that a component will perform its intended function without failure. Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability are two methods used to assess the reliability of a construct. Given that Cronbach's alpha is used to establish the minimum acceptable value of a construct, while composite reliability is used to assess the genuine reliability value, it follows that the composite reliability value will consistently surpass the value of Cronbach's alpha. Reliability of the construction is established when both Cronbach's alpha and the composite reliability values above 0.6 and 0.7, respectively (Ibbett et al., 2022).

Table 3. Composite Reliability

Variable	Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Product (X1)		0,881	0,914
Destination Quality	0,716		
Destination	0,827		
Uniqueness	0,886		
Tourist Attractions	0,853		
Comfort	0,832		
Security			
Price (X2)		0,923	0,942
Price	0,824		
competitiveness	0,895		
Tour package prices	0,881		
Discounts	0,893		
Price Affordability	0,878		
Price match			
Promotion (X3)		0,930	0,948
Social Media	0,775		
Interaction			
Discount campaign	0,935		
Customer testimonials	0,905		
Availability of Online Information	0,885		
Promotional quality	0,920		
Place (X4)		0,883	0,915
Accessibility	0,826		
Accommodation facilities	0,814		
Availability of tourist services	0,799		
Destination attractiveness	0,850		
Destination location	0,839		
Process (X5)		0,939	0,805
Quality of training	0,879		

Variable	Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Availability of Information	0,908		
Destination cleanliness	0,905		
Tourist experience Service	0,889		
People (X6)		0,928	0,776
Tour guide competency	0,817		
Credibility of the tour guide	0,905		
Communication Quality	0,916		
Responsive tour guide service	0,887		
Tour guide interaction with tourists	0,877		
Physical of Eviden (X7)	0,783	0,915	0,748
Physical Conditions of the Destination Environment	0,884		
Use of Technology	0,854		
Destination design	0,891		
Tourist Information Supervision	0,906		
Packaging (X8)		0,905	0,725
Selection of destination images	0,834		
Branding consistency	0,804		
Informative tour package packaging	0,901		
Availability of tour packages	0,861		
Quality of destination facilities	0,855		
Positioning (X9)		0,933	0,789
Destination image	0,884		
Brand identity	0,883		
Tourist segmentation	0,897		
Uniqueness of attraction	0,895		
Reputation			
Satisfaction (Y1)		0,905	0,779
Product Quality	0,851		
Service quality	0,896		
Ease of access	0,910		
accessibility			
Tourist experience	0,872		
Sustainable (Y2)		0,879	0,773
Intention to return to the destination	0,884		
Recommend destinations	0,856		
Tourist trust	0,844		
Tourist satisfaction	0,841		

Source: primary data processed, 2023

Table 3 indicates that all variables have alpha values of 0.60 or higher and composite reliability values of 0.70 or higher. Consequently, it can be confidently stated that all indicators and variables included in this study are reliable.

2. Inner Model Analysis

The objectives of inner models, often referred to as structural model testing, are to anticipate causal links and verify hypotheses regarding interconnected variables (Widyastuti & Puspita, 2020). This study is conducted to assess the R-squared and Goodness-of-Fit statistics, and will be followed by a test of the hypothesized association between the variables.

Figure 3. Full Research Mode

a. R - Square

The R-Square statistic quantifies the degree to which an exogenous element influences an endogenous factor. The R-squared values of 76.0 and 72.9 for the individual models imply a strong model and a moderately strong model, respectively (Ghozali, 2015).

Table 4. R-Square

Variable	R-Square
Satisfaction	76,0 %
Sustainable	72,9%

Source: primary data processed, 2023

Based on the information shown in Table 4, it is evident that the level of long-term customer satisfaction is 0.76 (76.0%), but the level of long-term sustainable customer satisfaction is 0.729%. The findings indicate that the model satisfies the moderate requirements, since all variables have R square values greater than 0.33 and less than 0.07.

b. Goodness-fit

The goodness-of-fit metric is employed to assess the efficacy of data collecting and study design models, and to offer a concise measure for all predictions made by the model. Based on the criteria established by Ghozali (2015) for goodness-of-fit values, a goodness-of-fit value of 0.10 suggests a little fit, a value of 0.25 shows a moderate fit, and a value of 0.36 indicates a high fit.

c. Hypothesis test

Assessing the amount of significance between the t-statistic and the p-value can assist in determining whether to accept or reject a hypothesis. The study's significance threshold was established at 5%. Consequently, the t-statistic employed was 1.96, which falls short of the criteria for the t-statistic to exceed 1.96 (Ghozali, 2015).

Table 5. Path Coefficients

Variable	T- Statistics (O/STDEV)	P-Values
H1 Product => Satisfaction	0,302	0,763*
H2 Price => Satisfaction	1,340	0,181*
H3 Promotion => Satisfaction	2,237	0,026 **
H4 Place => Satisfaction	0,599	0,549*
H5 Process => Satisfaction	0,675	0,500*
H6 People => Satisfaction	2,987	0,003 **
H7 Physical of Eviden => Satisfaction	1,443	0,150*
H8 Packaging => Satisfaction	2,307	0,021**
H9 Positioning => Satisfaction	4,497	0,000**
H10 Satisfaction => Sustainable	4,821	0,000**
H11 Packaging (X8) => Sustainable => Satisfaction	2,248	0,025**
H12 Positioning (X9) => Sustainable => Satisfaction	2,173	0,030**

*Significant at $p < 0.05$, **significant at $p < 0.01$

We determine that the product does not have a statistically significant impact on customer satisfaction by utilizing a T-statistic of $0.302 > 1.96$ and a P-value of $0.763 > 0.05$ for the path coefficient. The data indicate that hypothesis H1 is accurate in asserting that the product has a positive and insignificant impact on contentment. These results are consistent with the findings of prior research conducted by (Mim et al., 2022), which all demonstrated that the product had a positive and insignificant impact on the probability of returning visitors.

The path coefficient results indicated a non-significant relationship between price and satisfaction, as indicated by a T-statistic of $1.340 < 1.96$ and a P-value of $0.181 > 0.05$. We can infer from these statistical calculations that hypothesis H2 suggests that pricing has a positive and statistically insignificant impact on happiness. The results of these studies are in stark contrast to those of (Karsono & Salma, 2023), who discovered that consumers are more inclined to make a purchase if the product's price, promotion, location, physical evidence, people, procedures, productivity, and priority are all high. Islamic travel agencies.

The Influence of Promotion on Happiness, The path coefficient's results are statistically significant when the T-statistic is greater than or equal to 1.96 and the P-value is less than or equal to 0.02 . It is possible to infer that hypothesis H3 shows that advertising has a positive and significant impact on consumer contentment based on these statistical calculations. Promotions, which are also referred to as marketing communications (Kotler & Amstrong, 2018), are a diverse array of strategies that are employed to inform, remind, and engage consumers about a product or brand that is being offered, both directly and indirectly. The results are consistent with those of a study conducted by (Ghaleb Magatef Elham Fakhri Tomalieh, 2015), which determined that the satisfaction of visitors from outside Jordan was most significantly influenced by product and promotion.

The T-statistic of 20.751 is greater than 1.96 , and the P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ suggests that the impact of location on happiness is not statistically significant. The statistical calculations indicate that hypothesis H4 implies that location has a positive and statistically insignificant impact on happiness. These results are consistent with the findings of previous research conducted by (Mim et al., 2022), which demonstrated that the product had a positive and statistically insignificant impact on the likelihood of visitors returning.

A non-significant influence of the procedure on satisfaction is indicated by path coefficient results with T-statistics > 1.96 and P-value > 0.05 . Hypothesis H5 posits that the process has a positive and insignificant impact on happiness, as indicated by these statistical calculations. The results of this study are consistent with those of (Karsono & Salma, 2023), who determined that consumers are influenced to purchase halal tourist services by a variety of factors, such as product, price, promotion, place, physical evidence, people, procedures, productivity, and priority.

A statistically significant effect is observed in the path coefficient, with the influence of individuals on happiness (T-statistics > 2.987 , p-value 0.003). It is possible to infer that the H6 hypothesis demonstrates that humans have a positive and substantial influence on happiness based on these statistical calculations. The results of this study are consistent with those of (Karsono & Salma, 2023), who determined that consumers are influenced to purchase halal tourist services by a variety of factors, such as product, price, promotion, place, physical evidence, people, procedures, productivity, and priority.

The importance of tangible evidence Customers' satisfaction was not statistically significantly affected by the path coefficient results (T-statistics = $1.443 < 1.96$, and P-value = $0.150 > 0.05$). Based on these statistical calculations, it is evident that the H7 Hypothesis is positively and non-significantly influenced by physical evidence. Contentment The results of this study are consistent with those of a previous study conducted by Lorena Dara Putri Karsono and Laila Fairuz Salma (2023), which determined that a customer's willingness to pay for halal tourism services is influenced by a variety of factors, including product, price, promotion, location, tangible evidence, people, processes, output, and priority.

The path coefficient results indicate that packaging has a substantial impact on customer satisfaction when the T-statistic is greater than 2.307 and the P-value is less than 0.021 . The hypothesis that packing has a positive and significant impact on contentment is substantiated by this statistical analysis. The results of this study are consistent with those of a previous study conducted by Liao and Chuang (2020), which determined that package tourism had a statistically significant and positive impact on the overall satisfaction of travelers with their vacation.

The path coefficient results indicate a statistically significant effect of location on happiness, as indicated by a T-statistic of $4.497 > 1.96$ and a P-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This statistical analysis corroborates the hypothesis that placement has a statistically significant and positive impact on happiness. The results of this study corroborate the findings of previous research, including Sustainable Rural Tourism: An Indigenous Community Perspective on Positioning Rural Tourism (Falak et al., 2016).

A statistically significant influence of happiness on sustainability is revealed by path coefficient results with T-statistics greater than 1.96 and P-values less than 0.00005 . The H10 hypothesis predicts that happiness has a positive and substantial impact on sustainability, as indicated by the data. The results of this study are consistent with those of a previous study conducted by Loupias et al. (2023), which

determined that the frequency of visitors' returns to a specific destination was positively and statistically significantly influenced by their satisfaction levels.

The path coefficient results demonstrate the positive and statistically significant impact of packaging on sustainability, as mediated by satisfaction. The T-statistic is $2,248 > 1,96$, and the P-value is $0.025 < 0.05$. The data presented in Hypothesis H11 allows us to infer that packaging has a positive and substantial impact on sustainability, as mediated by happiness. The results of this study are consistent with the conclusions of prior research, which concluded that sustainability is a significant factor for package tourism (Goffi et al., 2019).

The positive impact of placement on sustainability is statistically significant when path coefficients have T-statistics of $2,173 > 1,96$ and P-values of $0.030 < 0.05$. The statistical calculations indicate that sustainability is positively and significantly influenced by placement, which corroborates hypothesis H12. The findings of this study are consistent with those of previous research, including Anne Hardy et al.'s 2002 sustainable tourism: an overview of the concept and its position in relation to conceptualisations of tourism and (Weaver et al., 2022) sustainable tourism: a framework for the future. Positioning residents as "the citizens within" to promote sustainable tourism.

Identification of Issues The purpose of this study was to assess and analyze the impact of the marketing mix for tourism destinations on repeat visits by tourists, as per respondents from the tourism industry in Kabupaten samosir, Pokdarwis, and tourists who visited the Hutatinggi tourist destination and the Dinas Pariwisata and Ekonomi Kreatif. This will enable Desa Hutatinggi to upgrade its tourist classification from "developing" to "self-sufficient." This would indirectly contribute to the government's objective of establishing 244 tourist villages that are autonomously classified as "tourism villages" by 2024.. Furthermore, the government has implemented a community-based tourism policy that emphasizes the role of the local population as tour operators.

Two, consistently motivate and encourage local residents to enhance the productivity of the tourism industry and the quality of the environment; and three, develop tourist attractions that utilize local resources and educate visitors about the culture and traditions of the area surrounding tourist villages. It is anticipated that this initiative will also contribute to the village of Hutatinggi's increased self-sufficiency by stimulating the local economy through tourism. The primary objective of the program, according to a village representative, is to encourage individuals in the village to consider innovative ways to enhance their quality of life in response to inquiries regarding the event's objectives and expectations. The respondent expects that the local community will be able to consider the possibility that a vacation in a rural location could enhance the quality of life for individuals. The transformation of a rural area into a tourist destination is contingent upon the implementation of community development initiatives. Consequently, it is anticipated that the implementation of this initiative will result in a significant improvement in the tourism sector of Desa Hutatinggi.

Conclusion

The study's findings are that the product, price, location, procedures, and tangible evidence all have positive and insignificant effects on the satisfaction of visitors with their time spent in a rural tourist destination. The reason for this discrepancy is that the variables in question have been associated with varying relationships in various studies. According to the author's research, the variables of product, price, location, process, and physical evidence all have a positive and non-statistically significant effect on the happiness of tourists, whereas the aforementioned variables have a positive and statistically significant effect on the happiness of tourists, as demonstrated by numerous studies. This assertion is corroborated by research conducted in Pekanbaru. Tourist satisfaction is comparatively unaffected by product, price, location, process, and physical evidence, according to research findings. Variables such as environmental factors, service quality, and visitors' preferences and expectations can influence this.

Visitors are positively and significantly influenced by promotion, people, packaging, positioning, satisfaction, sustainability, sustainable packaging as mediated by satisfaction, and sustainable positioning as mediated by satisfaction. This is due to the fact that effective advertising can increase consumers' awareness, interest, and knowledge, thereby increasing their confidence in their decision to spend additional time in the Hutatinggi tourist district. While Community Participation Can Generate Extended Tourist Itineraries. Unique and captivating travel package designs have the potential to captivate tourists and encourage them to embark on extended journeys. The genuine challenge is in determining the optimal locations to offer vacation packages in order to encourage tourists to extend their visits to the Hutatinggi tourist village.

The following recommendations are made in accordance with the data analysis conducted in this study:

1. Using digital platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube, as well as other social media platforms, is one of the most effective methods of disseminating information about a tourist destination and encouraging visitors to schedule a trip. Virtual reality platforms that are three-dimensional, such as Metaverse, can further disseminate information.
2. It is crucial that the packaging or wrapping of tour packages be innovative and creative in order to facilitate the easy acquisition of comprehensive information about the tourist destination by tourists. Especially when vacation packages are offered that include return flight tickets and refreshments for tourists, these offers may be difficult to resist. Upon arrival at your vacation destination, you will not be required to spend time in search of a hotel, restaurant, or any other amenities.
3. In order to elevate the region from its current status as a developing tourist destination to a fully-fledged tourist mecca, Hutatinggi should be strategically branded to establish itself as a premier tourist destination, thereby increasing the number of visitors. Further research should be conducted to gain a comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to the satisfaction of tourists, and this research should consider their preferences, motivations, and physical surroundings.

Ethics and consent

The Health Research Ethics Committee of Universitas Prima Nusantara Bukittinggi, West Sumatra, Indonesia has approved the conduct of the study on 17 April 2023; with reference number 261/KEPK/UPNB/IV/2023 (Certificate of passing the ethics review). The Committee confirmed that the study met the criteria that subject risk was minimised; subjects were selected fairly; honoured informed consent was provided and has been well documented and privacy and confidentiality were maintained. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

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